

Moral Sensitivity and Holistic Teaching Competence of Teachers in Cateel, Davao Oriental

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Abstract. Fundamentally, moral sensitivity was a measure expected to improve the holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers. In this study, the researcher selected elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, as the respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental were described as extensive. Meanwhile, correlation analysis demonstrated that there was a significant relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental. Evidently, regression analysis proved that moral sensitivity in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility were significant predictors of holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental. However, the researcher recommends conducting further analysis on other factors that influence the holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental since moral sensitivity only contributed 32.70 percent of the total variability.

KEY WORDS

1. moral sensitivity
2. holistic teaching competence of teachers
3. educational management

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1. Introduction

In today's world, countries willing to be more democratic, successful, and developed than others need to educate generations to have the required skills of the twenty-first century. In this sense, a learning and teaching environment appropriate for the 21st century and teachers need these skills. In terms of 21st-century skills, teachers are expected to guide and support their students' production readiness, curiosity, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking. 21st-century skills are divided into three main

themes: learning and innovation, knowledge, technology and media skills, and life and career skills. Thus, the development of twenty-first-century skills will also contribute positively to the future of students. Therefore, learning methods and strategies addressing the twenty-first century should be encouraged. In addition, learners should be provided with skills such as communication, collaboration, problem-solving, critical thinking, and productivity. Literature shows that the inability of teachers to employ holistic teaching approaches remains

of the teachers in all levels remains a perennial problem worldwide. For instance, Yariv (2014) noted that poor holistic teaching leads to ineffective classroom management strategies, resulting in disruptions, disciplinary issues, and challenges in maintaining a positive learning environment. The classroom may become less conducive to learning, affecting both the academic and socio-emotional development of students. Kıyasoğlu (2019) also noted that teachers using a poor holistic approach may neglect to address diverse learning styles and preferences among students. Students with different learning needs may struggle to grasp concepts, leading to disparities in understanding and academic achievement. More so, holistic teaching involves addressing socio-emotional aspects, such as emotional intelligence and social skills. A poor holistic approach may neglect these aspects. On the contrary, Kuloğlu and Karabekmez (2022) mentioned that teachers with holistic teaching competence are characterized as unbiased, patient, receptive to all kinds of innovations, and able to think in varied ways. Those teachers willing to increase their productivity should organize all the tools and materials within their reach in accordance with critical thinking skills. In the process of teaching critical thinking, Eğmir and Çengelci (2020) argue that teachers with holistic teaching competence encourage learners to discuss and question the information they suspect. They make sure that the communication in the classroom is clear and simple without imposing their own opinions on the learners. Bingöl (2019) also argued that teachers with holistic teaching competence help learners be able to think critically, create appropriate environments for critical thinking, actively participate in the activity, and develop a more advanced level of critical thinking ability. On one hand, Ineichen et al. (2017) defines moral sensitivity as the ability to recognize moral issues when they arise in practice. As highlighted by Christen et al. (2015),

moral sensitivity is related to personal agency within interpersonal relationships and can be expressed as a genuine concern for the welfare of others. In addition, Moosavi and Izadi (2018) believe moral sensitivity to be the awareness of how one's actions can affect others, making the nurse aware of moral problems that could arise while caring for others. Also, Rashvand et al. (2017) asserted that moral sensitivity implies awareness of moral duties and obligations and recognizing them when the professional considers the individual client's viewpoint in a moral dilemma. Thus, moral responsibility makes client attention and care possible because it is directed toward others and contributes to action. On the other hand, separate research indicates that moral sensitivity and holistic competence are essential in providing contexts. As an example, Nazari et al. (2022) mentioned that the possible reason for an indirect correlation between the quality of care and moral sensitivity could be that the service providers are forced to make decisions and shoulder duties that cause contradictions between personal values and professional values. Adding more, Mariona (2016) described that a service provider who follows the holistic approach considers the uniqueness of each person and respects their personal beliefs and values. While following the holistic approach, a nurse considers the individual's social support resources, health practices, experiences related to their personal and family health, disease patterns, personality traits, social and cultural characteristics, nutrition habits, ways of stress management, and life habits such as rest and exercise. The gap between previous studies (Mariona, 2016; Nazari et al., 2022) is that those studies were conducted in a foreign setting. Also, those studies were conducted in a general service provider context. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine context, particularly in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, using a quantitative research

design. Specifically, the researcher used a correlational approach to understand better the relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic competence in an educational context, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding the direct influence of moral sensitivity on the holistic teaching competence of the teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

1.1. *Review of Related Literature—*

1.1.1. *Moral Sensitivity—*Moral sensitivity is the ability to recognize and appropriately respond to moral issues in practice. It involves both intuitive recognition and deliberative processes, guiding moral action through emotional and cognitive responses (Ineichen et al., 2017; Moosavi et al., 2017; Lützn et al., 2012). It incorporates moral strength, moral burden, and moral responsibility. Moral strength entails the courage to act ethically despite challenges (Baykara et al., 2015; Sekerka Bagozzi, 2012). Moral burden refers to the stress experienced when professional and personal values conflict (Takizawa et al., 2021). Moral responsibility focuses on acting ethically to promote the welfare of others (McShane Von Glinow, 2016; Segon Booth, 2017).

Moral sensitivity influences organizational performance, as a strong work ethic and ethical culture enhance individual and organizational outcomes (Petyx et al., 2016; Edison et al., 2016). Conversely, moral blindness or the lack of moral sensitivity can result in actions that conflict with personal values, affecting professional relationships and patient care (Bazerman Tenbrunsel, 2014; Sa Sah, 2019).

1.1.2. *Holistic Teaching Competence—*Holistic teaching aims to activate all aspects of a learner's personality for effective and comprehensive learning. It involves addressing emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs in an integrated manner (Pérez-Guilarte et al., 2022; Mahmoudi et al., 2017). Holistic education cultivates a child's physical, emotional, moral,

psychological, and spiritual development in a supportive environment (Lauricella MacAskill, 2015; Hare, 2014). Effective pedagogical strategies include student-centered approaches, cooperative learning, and technology integration to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes (Temli-Dumus, 2016; Kristiansen et al., 2019).

Holistic teaching competence is measured through indicators like general aptitude, education management, ethically oriented practices, and professional development. General aptitude involves positive work behaviors that enhance organizational well-being (Biggs et al., 2014). Teacher education management focuses on maintaining best practices through continuous learning and development (Schleicher, 2021). Ethically oriented practices require adherence to organizational values, fostering trust and professionalism (Petty Hill, 2017). Professional development is crucial for skill enhancement and effective teaching, impacting student achievement and teacher satisfaction (Jones Dexter, 2016; Tanang Abu, 2014).

Relationship Between Moral Sensitivity and Holistic Teaching Competence Studies show a significant relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence. Moral sensitivity, involving ethical decision-making and handling moral tensions, impacts holistic teaching, which integrates ethical, emotional, and academic support (Nazari et al., 2022; Amiri et al., 2019). Ethical behavior in teaching promotes employability and enhances organizational commitment (Sliter et al., 2016; Lavicoli et al., 2018).

1.2. *Synthesis—*Therefore, this portion of the paper provides the researcher with the discussions of literature and the results of other research to which the present study is related or has some bearing and similarity. More so, the literature showed that moral sensitivity, as proposed by Ineichen et al. (2017), is measured in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden,

and moral responsibility, while holistic teaching competence, as proposed by Pérez-Guilarte et al. (2022) is measured in terms of general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practices, and professional development. Also, studies derived from several theoretical perspectives have confirmed several assumptions about moral sensitivity is connected with the holistic teaching competence of the teachers. This gives the author sufficient background to understand the study.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—This study was anchored on the proposition of Nazari et al. (2022) that the possible reason for an indirect correlation between the quality of care and moral sensitivity could be that the service providers are forced to make decisions and shoulder duties that cause contradictions between personal values and professional values. In support, Amiri et al. (2019) proposed that there is a significant inverse relationship between the score of holistic teaching competence and the dimension of moral sensitivity; it seems that when teachers make moral decisions, they experience a conflict between personal and professional values in their careers and thus experience moral tension. Accordingly, if this tension is not resolved correctly, it can provide a way for them to distance themselves from clients, making service providers indifferent to moral care. Figure 1 presents the study's conceptual framework, which helped the researcher summarize and briefly state the concept of the study. The independent variable is the moral sensitiv-

ity or the ability to recognize moral issues when they arise in practice. According to Ineichen et al. (2017), the measures of moral sensitivity are moral strength or the experience of excessive and idiosyncratic desires. Nevertheless, resisted among individuals; a sense of moral burden in the situation in which there is a discrepancy between the moral values of professionals and clients that can generate negative feelings of stress, frustration, or guilt; and moral responsibility or the relevant action that breaches or upholds general moral norms, such as preventing harm or promoting the welfare of others. The dependent variable of the study is the holistic teaching approach, which is conceptualized by Pérez-Guilarte et al. (2022) and defined as the approach that seeks to fully activate all aspects of the learner's personality (intellect, emotions, imagination, and body) for more effective and comprehensive learning. The measures of the holistic teaching approach are general aptitude or the general behaviors as a person rather than as a teacher; teacher education management or the process of directing teams and teaching departments to maintain best practices and organization when providing services; ethically oriented practices or the extent in which a service care provider obey the organization's rules; and professional development or the process of learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in teaching practice.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary objective of this study was to determine which domain of moral sensitivity significantly

influences the holistic teaching competence of the teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Thus, the result of the study sought the answer to the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of moral sensitivity of the elementary school teachers in terms of:
 - (1) moral strength;
 - (2) sense of moral burden; and
 - (3) moral responsibility?

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

- (2) What is the extent of holistic teaching competence of the elementary school teachers in terms of:
- (1) general aptitude;
 - (2) teacher education management
 - (3) ethically oriented practices; and
 - (4) professional development?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of the teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental?
- (4) Which domain of moral sensitivity significantly influences the holistic teaching competence of the teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental?

1.5. *Hypotheses*—The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of the teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. H02: None of the domains of moral sensitivity significantly influence the holistic teaching competence of the teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Conducting a study on the moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of teachers can yield valuable insights for various stakeholders in the education system. Here were the benefits for the Department of Education, school principals, teachers, and future researchers: Department of Education. Understanding the relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence can inform the development of policies emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations in teacher training and professional development. Insights from the study can

contribute to the integration of moral and ethical components into teacher education curricula, ensuring that future educators are equipped with the necessary skills and values. School Heads. Principals can use the findings to guide teachers' recruitment and professional development. Emphasizing moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence in hiring and training practices can contribute to a positive school culture. The study can inform the development of evaluation criteria that assess academic performance and the moral and holistic aspects of teaching competence, providing a more comprehensive measure of teacher effectiveness. Teachers. The study could benefit teachers by providing insights into the importance of moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence. This knowledge can guide their professional development efforts, encouraging them to enhance their ethical decision-making skills and holistic teaching approaches. The study may also promote self-

reflection among teachers, encouraging them to assess their own moral sensitivity and holistic teaching practices. This introspection can lead to improved teaching strategies and a greater focus on ethical considerations in the classroom. Future researchers. The study serves as a foundation for future research endeavors, encouraging scholars to explore additional dimensions of moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence. This can lead to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between teachers' moral values and their teaching practices. For

a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: In this study, moral sensitivity refers to the independent variable being described in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility. Holistic Teaching Competence. This study describes the dependent variable in terms of the following indicators: general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practices, and professional development.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study, the researcher. Quantitative research, as described by Bhandari (2020), is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research is described as research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013),

descriptive-correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher looked into the relationship between two variables—moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of the teachers. In this connection, the study focused on exploring which domains of the attitude toward digital technology significantly influence the instructional supervision skills of the teachers. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to experiment with a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. The 155

respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there was heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve its purpose. Hence, only those permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Cateel 1 District, Davao Oriental, who voluntarily signed the ICF, were given the survey

questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed researcher-made questionnaires, which were contextualized to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument is concerned with the moral sensitivity of the teachers. This questionnaire comprised statements divided among the indicators: moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility. The scale's reliability obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.982, which was described as excellent and interpreted as very reliable. The adapted instrument made use of a 5-point Likert scale and was determined based on the following ranges of means:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Moral sensitivity is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	Moral sensitivity is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Moral sensitivity is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	Moral sensitivity is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	Moral sensitivity is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the holistic teaching competence. The questionnaires were composed of statements divided among the indicators: general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practices, and professional development. The Cronbach alpha value for the new scale is 0.910, meaning the instrument is reliable and consis-

tent. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of the holistic teaching competence of the teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80.

Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments.

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The holistic teaching competence of the teachers is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The holistic teaching competence of the teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The holistic teaching competence of the teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The holistic teaching competence of the teachers is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The holistic teaching competence of the teachers is never manifested.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study, and the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate is attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the principals of the selected public elementary schools in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after they had been approved to conduct the study. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. The study was done in the fourth quarter of the school year 2022-2023 to administer the questionnaire. More so, the study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following

the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were adequately informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were provided to help them better understand the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refused to participate, the researcher did not force them. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the holistic teaching competence of the teachers as determined by moral sensitivity and that may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study's respondents were teachers, so they were not considered vulnerable since all of them were of legal age, and they were not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the re-

spondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, which were the natural source of information, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, the access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the data on the survey. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed of all the survey questionnaires and deleted the data results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the natural sources of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and adequately the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they

would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study—anybody who fits the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher respected the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier and sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication concerning the research was done honestly and fairly. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher correctly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Notably, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that other factors like the conflict of interest did not influence the respondents' responses. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study, the

Division of Davao Oriental was given a furnished copy of the research results so that the respondents could access them and use them for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials that were ample and available during the study, which was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by adequately encoding the respondents' ratings during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every research phase, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to

apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence. It was used to supply the answers for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (moral sensitivity) and dependent (holistic teaching competence). It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . Multiple linear regression analysis was applied to evaluate the significance of which domains of the independent (moral sensitivity) variable significantly influence the dependent (holistic teaching competence) variable.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of teachers, the significant relationship among the variables, and the influence of moral sensitivity on the holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

3.1. Moral Sensitivity of Elementary School Teachers—

3.1.1. Moral Strength—This dimension of the moral strength of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, acquired a mean score of 3.25, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. In addition, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.98 to 3.67. The item, believing that I have an excellent ability to notice when patients are not receiving adequate care, reflects a mean rating of 2.98, described as

moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes observed. The item, having a good understanding of what kind of consideration is required as a teacher when explaining difficult things, or things that are hard to talk about with the learners and other stakeholders, acquired a mean rating of 3.67, described as extensive and interpreted as item is oftentimes observed. The result indicates that teachers with high levels of moral strength exhibit a deep awareness of moral issues and the inner strength to act according to their ethical beliefs, even in challenging situations.

Table 1. Moral Sensitivity of Teachers in Terms of Moral Strength

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Having the ability to notice the needs of learners well has been useful during teaching-learning processes.	3.09	Moderately Extensive
2. Believing that I have an excellent ability to notice when patients are not receiving adequate care.	2.98	Moderately Extensive
3. Having a good understanding of what kind of consideration is required as a teacher when explaining difficult things or things that are hard to talk about with the learners and other stakeholders.	3.67	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.25	Moderately Extensive

This agrees with the idea of Moosavi and Izadi (2018) that teachers with high moral strength exhibit a consistent commitment to ethical decision-making, ensuring that their choices prioritize the well-being and development of students. Making decisions that align with ethical principles, values, and professional standards. More so, teachers with high moral strength are powerful role models, demonstrating the importance of honesty, responsibility, and compassion in their daily interactions with students and colleagues.

3.1.2. *Sense of Moral Burden*—Concerning the moral sensitivity of teachers in terms of a sense of moral burden, the table reflects a category mean of 3.69, described as exten-

The result means that teachers recognize the weight of their role in shaping students' character and guiding them toward ethical behavior. The result corresponds with Syahrul Nizam et al. (2016) idea that teachers with a high sense of moral burden are committed to incorporating ethical instruction into their lessons, ensuring that students receive guidance on moral values and principles. They are prioritizing the integration of ethical and moral content in the

sive, which is interpreted as the moral sensitivity of teachers is oftentimes observed among elementary teachers in Cateel 1 District, Davao Oriental. It can be shown that the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.34 to 4.01. The item, Feeling terrible when caring for a learner suffering because of feeling helpless, has a mean rating of 3.34, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. Whereas, the item Avoiding the thought that I can leave things as they are when I notice something about a learner's feelings has a mean of 4.01, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed by elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

curriculum. In addition, Joshi and Jain (2016) mentioned that teachers with a strong sense of moral burden take the time to understand each student's moral development, offering guidance and support tailored to their individual needs.

3.1.3. *Moral Responsibility*—Concerning Moral Responsibility, it reflects a category mean of 3.45, described as extensive, which is interpreted as the moral sensitivity of teachers of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1,

Table 2. Moral Sensitivity of Teachers in Terms of Sense of Moral Burden

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Feeling terrible when caring for a learner who is suffering because of feeling helpless.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
2. It makes me feel terrible when I see a learner who is suffering from learning deficiency.	3.44	Extensive
3. Feeling downcast if I notice a learner’s need because they might have other needs as well.	3.98	Extensive
4. Avoiding the thought that I can leave things as they are when I notice something about a learner’s feelings.	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.69	Extensive

Davao Oriental is oftentimes observed. It can be shown that the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.07 to 3.86. The item Supporting the development of high-level thinking skills of the students has obtained a mean rating of 3.07, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Whereas, the item Supporting the development of question asking, the questioning and research skills has a mean of 3.87, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed by the elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

Table 3. Moral Sensitivity of Teachers in Terms of Moral Responsibility

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Supporting the development of question-asking, questioning, and research skills.	3.86	Extensive
2. Supporting the development of high-level thinking skills (e.g., critical thinking, creative thinking, etc.) of the students.	3.07	Moderately Extensive
3. Supporting the development of the problem-solving skills of the students.	3.56	Extensive
4. Supporting the development of purpose determination and the realization skills of the students.	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.45	Extensive

The result implies that teachers with high moral responsibility understand their profound impact on students’ moral development and take deliberate actions to fulfill their ethical obligations. This supports Takizawa et al.’s (2021) idea that teachers with a strong sense of moral responsibility are consistent role models, demonstrating ethical behavior in their actions and interactions and providing a tangible example for students to follow. This also supports Segon and Booth’s (2017) findings that teachers with a sense of moral responsibility actively

cultivate a culture of integrity, emphasizing the importance of honesty, responsibility, and ethical behavior within the classroom and school community and creating an educational environment that values integrity and ethical conduct.

3.2. *The Summary of The Extent of Moral Sensitivity Of Elementary School Teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental*—Overall, the results in Table 4 reflect the summary of the extent of moral sensitivity of elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. The overall mean score on the moral sensitiv-

ity of teachers of elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, is 3.46, which was described as extensive. As shown in the table, the moral sensitivity of teachers in terms of the sense of moral burden acquired the highest mean score of 3.69. In contrast, the moral sensitivity of teachers in terms of moral strength was rated with the lowest mean score of 3.25, which was described as moderately extensive among elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

Table 4. Summary on Moral Sensitivity of Teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Moral Strength	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Sense of Moral Burden	3.69	Extensive
Moral Responsibility	3.45	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.46	Extensive

The results imply that teachers’ ability to recognize, interpret, and appropriately respond to moral issues, dilemmas, and values inherent in teaching and interactions with students, colleagues, and the broader school community is oftentimes observed among elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. This is congruent with Jordan’s (2016) view that teachers with high moral sensitivity consistently make ethically informed decisions, ensuring that their choices prioritize the well-being and development of students. They make decisions aligned with ethical principles, values, and professional standards. Moreover, the result is in agreement with Lützn et al.’s (2012) idea that teachers with high moral sensitivity contribute to creating a positive moral climate, fostering a sense of respect, responsibility, and fairness within the learning community and establishing a classroom and school environment that promotes ethical behavior and values.

3.3. *Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary School Teachers in Cateel District 1 Davao Oriental*—

3.3.1. *General Aptitude*—This domain, as shown in Table 5, has a category mean of 3.66, described as extensive, denoting that this particular domain of holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers is oftentimes manifested by the respondents in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Adding on, it can be shown that the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.66 to 4.00. The lowest mean item, Spending effort to identify the reasons behind the existing problems and offer solutions for them, obtained a mean rating of 2.66, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. The item, Trying to enhance the well-being of others with all my power, obtained a mean rating of 4.00, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents, the elementary teachers in

Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. This means that the comprehensive set of skills, attributes, and capabilities that teachers possess, allowing them to address various aspects of students' development—academic, social, emotional, and physical is oftentimes observed among elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

Table 5. Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary School Teachers in Terms of General Aptitude

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Spending effort to identify the reasons behind the existing problems and offering solutions for them.	2.66	Moderately Extensive
2. Reflecting on and evaluating my own thinking processes thoroughly and objectively.	4.35	Very Extensive
3. Being aware of the differences between current and ideal selves.	3.97	Extensive
4. Trying to enhance the well-being of others with all my power.	4.00	Extensive
5. Consoling and encouraging other people when they are in a difficult situation.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.66	Extensive

This supports Koopmans’ (2014) idea that teachers with high general aptitude use differentiated instruction to address individual student needs, ensuring that all students can access and engage with the curriculum effectively. Likewise, this agrees with Biggs et al. (2014) findings that teachers with high general aptitude create holistic lesson plans that integrate various dimensions of learning, fostering a well-rounded educational experience for students. Designing lessons considering academic content and student development’s social, emotional, and physical aspects.

3.3.2. *Teacher Education Management*—Consequently, the dimension of teacher education management shown in Table 8 is extensive,

with a category mean of 3.87. This means that a holistic teaching approach in terms of teacher education management is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.55 to 4.19. The item, Trying to provide teaching services that are an example to other teachers, reflects a mean rating of 3.55, described as extensive, and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested. Further, the item Providing continuous training and guidance to each nurse while considering their competencies has a mean rating of 4.19, described as extensive, interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested by the respondents in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

The result shows that the comprehensive set of skills, knowledge, and strategies that teachers possess to manage and optimize the educational

experiences of their students effectively is oftentimes manifested by the elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

Table 6. Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary School Teachers in Terms of Teacher Education Management

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Trying to provide teaching services that is an example to other teachers.	3.55	Extensive
2. Helping to decide on a solution that is respectful of all opinions when there are conflicts among teachers.	4.02	Extensive
3. Providing continuous training and guidance to each teacher while taking their competencies into consideration.	4.19	Extensive
4. Creating an environment and culture that facilitates learning in the workplace.	3.67	Extensive
5. Facilitating the exchange of opinions by communication when there are conflicts among teachers.	4.10	Extensive
6. Helping other teachers with their self-learning.	3.67	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.87	Extensive

It agreed with the idea of Schleicher (2021) that teachers with high levels of competence in teacher education management strategically plan the curriculum, ensuring that it aligns with the holistic development of students and meets educational standards. They are designing a well-structured and comprehensive curriculum that addresses academic, social, and emotional learning goals. More so, teachers with solid education management skills implement differentiated instruction, addressing students' individual strengths, interests, and learning styles to promote holistic development.

3.3.3. *Ethically Oriented Practice*—The results in Table 7 showed that the domain of ethically oriented practice acquires an exten-

The result implies that the integration of ethical considerations and values into every aspect of teaching, encompassing academic instruction, classroom management, and interactions with students, colleagues, and parents, is oftentimes manifested by the elementary school teachers

sive category mean of 3.65, which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.05 to 4.12. The table further reveals that the item Making my own decisions during teaching practice and being responsible for them has a mean rating of 3.05, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Notifying other education professionals about the teacher's needs to improve learners, reflects a mean rating of 4.12, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. This result is similar to the view of Simonson et al. (2017) that teachers with ethically oriented practice provide students with opportunities to engage in meaningful discussions, fostering critical thinking and moral reasoning. Actively incorporating

Table 7. Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary School Teachers in Terms of Ethically Oriented Practice

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Providing learner-centred care regarding learners' rights and dignity.	3.32	Moderately Extensive
2. Following the main principles of teaching practices.	3.75	Extensive
3. Making my own decisions during teaching practice and being responsible for them.	3.05	Moderately Extensive
4. Notifying other education professionals about the teacher's needs to improve learners.	4.12	Extensive
5. Confirming that a task is properly completed when assigning the task to other teachers.	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.65	Extensive

discussions about ethical principles and dilemmas into lessons. More so, teachers with high levels of ethically oriented practice serve as role models, cultivating a classroom culture where ethical behavior is evident and emphasized.

3.3.4. *Professional Development*—This domain, as shown in Table 8, has a category mean of 3.62, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain of holistic teaching approach of elementary teachers is

oftentimes manifested by the respondents in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.26 to 4.21. Specifically, the item spending time and effort learning about and preserving the current information and skills necessary for teaching practice obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.26, which is moderately extensive and sometimes interpreted as an item manifested by respondents.

Table 8. Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary School Teachers in Terms of Professional Development

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Spending time and effort learning about and preserving the current information and skills which are necessary for teaching practice.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
2. Determining my own learning needs by seriously reflecting on my teaching practices.	3.45	Extensive
3. Creating a professional development plan for my personal development.	4.11	Extensive
4. Looking for immediate responses to the questions emerging from teaching practice.	4.21	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	3.62	Extensive

The item Looking for immediate responses to the questions emerging from teaching practice reflects the highest mean rating of 4.21. It is described as very extensive and interpreted as an item always manifested by the elementary school teacher of Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. This means that the continuous improvement, growth, and refinement of teaching practices that encompass not only academic proficiency but also the broader aspects of student development, classroom management, and teacher well-being is oftentimes manifested by the teachers. This is in agreement with the study of Jones and Dexter (2016) that teachers with a focus on professional development continuously update their teaching methods, ensuring they remain responsive to the evolving needs of students and the educational landscape and actively seeking opportunities for learning and adapting teaching strategies based on new knowledge and insights. Furthermore, Govranos and Newton

(2014) indicated that teachers committed to professional development incorporate innovative approaches, enhancing their ability to engage students and promote effective learning. Overall, the results in Table 9 reflect the summary of the extent of holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. The overall mean score on the holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, is 3.73, described as extensive. As shown in the table, holistic teaching competence in terms of teacher education management acquired the highest mean score of 3.87, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. In contrast, holistic teaching competence in terms of ethically oriented practice was rated with the lowest mean score of 3.65, which was described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested.

Table 9. Summary of Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary Teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
General Aptitude	3.66	Extensive
Teacher Education Management	3.87	Extensive
Ethically Oriented Practice	3.65	Extensive
Professional Development	3.76	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.73	Extensive

The result implies that the comprehensive set of skills, knowledge, and attitudes that extend beyond academic instruction is oftentimes manifested by the elementary school teacher in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. The result is congruent with Lauricella and MacAskill’s (2015) idea that high-level, holistic competence involves identifying and responding to individual student strengths and challenges, ensuring that each student receives personalized support for academic success. Moreover, the result is

similar to Hare’s (2014) assertion that teachers with high-level, holistic competence integrate SEL practices, recognizing the significance of emotional well-being in students’ overall development.

3.4. *Relationship Between Moral Sensitivity and Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary Teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental*—The analysis results on the relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers

in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 12 shows that moral sensitivity has a significant positive relationship with the holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .706$, $p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of moral sensitivity changes, the extent of holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in

Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, also significantly changes. Moreover, the table also shows that moral sensitivity in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility are significantly correlated with holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, as evident in the correlation coefficient values of 0.774, 0.635 and 0.801. This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

Table 10. Relationship Between Moral Sensitivity and Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary Teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental

Moral Sensitivity	r-value	p-value	Decision
Moral Strength	0.774*	0.000	Reject H0
Sense of Moral Burden	0.635*	0.000	Reject H0
Moral Responsibility	0.801*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Moral Sensitivity	0.706*	0.000	Reject H0

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$

The result implies that teachers with high moral sensitivity are more likely to make ethically informed decisions. Ethical decision-making is an integral part of holistic teaching. The findings support Ndungu’s (2014) assertion that modeling ethical behavior is essential for holistic teaching competence as it contributes to developing students’ character, social skills, and emotional well-being. Teachers with moral sensitivity serve as ethical role models for students. A positive moral climate is a key component of holistic teaching competence as it fosters a supportive environment conducive to overall student development.

Therefore, moral sensitivity predicts the holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

3.5. Influence of Moral Sensitivity on the Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary Teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental— The significance of the influence of moral sensitivity on the holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. Table 13 shows that when moral sensitivity is considered as a predictor of holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, the model is significant, as evident in an F-value of 20.377 with $p < 0.05$.

Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.327 indicates that moral sensitivity has contributed significantly to the variability of holistic

Table 11. Influence of Moral Sensitivity on the Holistic Teaching Competence of Elementary Teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental

Moral Sensitivity	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Moral Strength	0.391*	0.327	0.078	0.000	Reject H0
Sense of Moral Burden	0.124*	0.134	0.062	0.040	Reject H0
Moral Responsibility	0.232*	0.226	0.063	0.000	Reject H0

R² = 0.327
F-value = 20.377**
p-value = 0.000

Note. *Significant at p <0.05; **Significant at p <0.01

teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental by 32.70. In addition, the table shows that there are domains of moral sensitivity that significantly influence the holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. This table indicates that moral sensitivity in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility are significant when considered as predictor of holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers. This means that the extent of holistic teaching competence of the elementary teacher increases by 0.391, 0.124 and 0.232 for each unit increase in moral sensitivity of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Thus, this leads to the rejection of null hypothesis that none of the domain of the moral sensitivity significantly influence the holistic teaching competence of the elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao

Oriental. Affirming that holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers is a function of moral sensitivity, the finding is in agreement with the view of Amiri’s et al. (2019) that when teachers make moral decisions, they experience a conflict between personal and professional values in their careers and thus experience moral tension. Accordingly, if this tension is not resolved properly, it can provide a way for them to distance themselves from clients, making service providers indifferent to moral care. Lastly, the findings are in agreement with the anchored proposition by Nazari et al. (2022) that the possible reason for an indirect correlation between the quality of care and moral sensitivity could be that the service providers are forced to make decisions and shoulder duties that cause contradictions between personal values and professional values.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of moral sensitivity significantly influence the holistic teaching approach of elementary school teachers utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-predictive tech-

nique. The researcher selected 155 elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: The extent of moral sensitivity of the elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, has an overall mean of 3.46 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Meanwhile, moral sensitivity regarding moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility obtained the mean scores of 3.25, 3.69, and 3.45, respectively. The extent of holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, has an overall mean of 3.73 and a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, the holistic teaching competence of elementary school teachers in terms of general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practice, and professional development obtained mean scores of 3.66, 3.87, 3.65, and 3.76, respectively. The result showed that moral sensitivity has a significant positive relationship with the holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .706, p < 0.05$). This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental. Overall, moral sensitivity significantly influences the holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental, as evident by the F-value of 20.377 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.327 indicated that moral sensitivity has contributed significantly to the variability of holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1 in

Davao Oriental by 32.70 percent from the total variability. Moreover, moral sensitivity in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility was found to be significant predictors of holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1 in Davao Oriental as indicated by the regression coefficient values of 0.391, 0.124 and 0.232, respectively.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The moral sensitivity of the elementary school teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, was rated as extensive. The moral sensitivity of the elementary school teachers in terms of a sense of moral burden and moral responsibility was rated as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, the moral sensitivity of the elementary school teachers in terms of a sense of moral burden was rated as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. The results suggested that the ability to recognize moral issues in practice was often observed among elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. The holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, was extensive. The competence of elementary teachers in general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practice, and professional development was also rated as extensive. The result implies that the approach that seeks to fully activate all aspects of the learner's personality (intellect, emotions, imagination, body) for more effective and comprehensive learning was oftentimes observed by the elementary school teacher in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. The result showed that moral sensitivity has a significant positive relationship with the holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. This means that as the extent of moral sensitivity changes, the holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental,

also significantly changes. Moral sensitivity in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility significantly influenced the holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that no moral sensitivity domains significantly influence elementary teachers' holistic teaching competence in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental.

4.3. Recommendations—Department of Education and policymakers should conduct a seminar-workshop to develop moral sensitivity among teachers. The review of the teachers' moral sensitivity and professional behavior may be the main focus of this program. This could significantly contribute to maintaining the teachers' holistic teaching competence. Also, to create working habits that would consider their identity as a professional teacher, teachers should regularly attend professional development seminars. This would increase teachers' self-assurance in their abilities. Higher staff performance, productivity, and general morale can correlate with higher confidence levels. Another recommendation was to keep a teaching portfolio. Keeping a teaching portfolio was an effective professional development practice. Besides enhancing teachers' sense of accountability to-

ward their teaching, it provides a treasure trove of data to track their progress, analyze their performance over the years, identify what works and what does not and why, and design new strategies to meet emerging instructional needs. Reflective writing is an important element in a teacher's portfolio. It was a meta-cognitive act that allowed teachers to develop a heightened awareness of their 'ways of knowing not only about their students but also about themselves and their beliefs. Teachers may be engaged in co-teaching practices. Co-teaching is a useful activity for sharing and comparing teaching practices and getting ideas to help make teaching events special. It enhances teachers' reflective practice and enables them to enrich and expand their professional development. Furthermore, the study found that moral sensitivity only contributed to 32.70 percent of the total variability of holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental. Thus, the researcher recommends that other researchers should conduct an explanatory study on the mediating factors that cause the relationship between moral sensitivity and holistic teaching competence of elementary teachers in Cateel District 1, Davao Oriental, in a larger context should be conducted.

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